

Exploring the Meanings Underlying
Recreational Drug Use within the
Electronic Dance Music Scene in
England.

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Abstract

Raves and clubs have long been targeted as sites of excessive risk among health and law practitioners due to their relationship with dance drugs. Scholars who have also been interested in understanding drug use have focused on two contrasting traditions: the epidemiological tradition, which focuses on risk and protective factors of drug use, and the cultural studies tradition, which instead focuses on the pleasures and subjectivities of drug use, as well as its social context. Taking into account the perspective of cultural studies research and by including discourses around agency and risk management, this qualitative interview-based study explores drug use through the lived experience of the participants. This research has been specifically interested in the social context of underground raves and commercial nightclubs in England. This research adopts an appreciative approach which contrasts with official/government discourse and the epidemiological tradition. Indeed, this research portrays drug use as a meaningful and rational activity based upon discourses of risk management and pleasure.

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Chapter 1: Introduction

Since their appearance in the late 80s in the UK, underground raves and later clubs have been targeted as sites of excessive risk by health and law practitioners due to their relationship with illicit drugs (Hunt et al., 2009). The high prevalence of dance drugs among rave and club attendees (Coomber et al., 2013), has always been a source of public concern among the media and the wider population, resulting in significant actions being taken by government officials in order to constrain the subcultural movement of the late 80s (Hunt et al., 2010). Throughout the history of rave culture in England, different legislations have been passed in order to prevent people from gathering around music made of 'repetitive beats' (Weier, 2000). An indicator of this 'War on drugs' was the implementation of the Criminal Justice and Public order Act (1994) which led to a venue shift and the incorporation of raves within the nighttime economy of clubs (Coomber et al., 2013). Despite the effort made by government officials to fight drug use within the night time leisure of English people, dance drugs today still dominate dance floors across England.

The relationships between recreational drugs and the dance music scene has also been source of significant debate among scholarly work across the world, leading to two different traditions in understanding drug use within the night time leisure of people: the epidemiological tradition and the one of cultural-studies research (Hunt et al., 2009). The epidemiological approach, which relies on quantitative research methods, aims to understand drug use in terms of risk and protective factors, as well as the characteristics of the user to prevent and minimize drug-related risks (Williams and Parker, 2001). On the other hand, the perspective of cultural studies research relies on the 'subjective knowledge' of the users within their social contexts (Moore, 2008). That being said, it is important to clarify the direction in which this research is going towards. In order to explore the meanings underlying recreational drug use within the electronic dance music (EDM) scene in England, the perspective of cultural studies research has been chosen as the most suitable approach for the purposes of this dissertation. Here, the cultural studies tradition will allow to place the respective drug experiences of the participants interviewed through qualitative research methods within the social context of the EDM scene. By doing so, therefore, the researcher hopes to gain a deeper understanding of the underlying forces that lead people to consume recreational drugs at raves and clubs. Why are rave and club attendees more likely to take drugs? What are the purposes of taking drugs at raves and clubs? What is the reasoning behind drug use within the social reality of the EDM scene? Questions like such reveal a strong relationship between individual agency and the social context in which the drug experiences

are embedded and take meaning. Moreover, by adopting the perspective of cultural studies research and by taking into account the insider knowledge of the participants, the researcher hopes to alleviate the stigma surrounding drug use and the electronic dance music scene. This research will therefore, explore discourses around risk management and pleasure in relation to the rave and club realities, contributing towards filling the blind spots within cultural studies scholarships in the field of drug use and leisure. By doing so therefore, the research adopts a more appreciative approach that portrays users as rational individuals capable of negotiating their choices based upon a risk versus benefit analysis, while being influenced by their respective social contexts (Williams and Parker, 2001). Finally, this research hopes to give an opportunity for the unheard voices of millions of people who's night time leisure involves the use of illicit drugs.

Chapter 2: Literature Review

2.1 Introduction

In the light of this research, which is to explore the meanings that people involved in the electronic dance music (EDM) scene in England associate to their recreational drug use, this dissertation will now consider some of the most influential research in the fields of drug use and rave culture which will give a good idea of the choices made for this project. It will therefore begin by investigating what constitutes rave culture today as it will help clarify the focus of this dissertation.

2.2 Rave Culture Today

Rave culture originates in the late eighties when DJ Paul Oakenfold and other British DJs commuted to the famous Island of Ibiza where they discovered the new substance 'ecstasy' and a new sound influenced by Chicago House and Detroit Techno and later described as 'Acid House' (Coomber et al, 2013; Anderson and Kavanaugh, 2008). Amazed by the effects of the new substance and intrigued by the new sound from America, Oakenfold and friends decided to recreate the Ibiza music scene in England which caught the attention of new DJs and promoters and spread across British music capitals like London and Manchester (Reynolds, 2013). The 'underground' nature of British raves of the late eighties and early nighties, which is to some extent still present today, comes from a period where licensing laws in England were very strict. Therefore, unlicensed venues such as car parks, warehouses, as well as forests and fields were good solutions for DJs to promote their sound, which usually included a range of different electronic music genres such as house, techno, trance, hardcore, jungle, garage and many more (Sanders, 2006; Thornton 1996; Weier, 2000).

The relationship between raves and illicit drugs raised concerns among law and public health practitioners and resulted in the implementation of the Criminal Justice and Public Order Act (1994), which aimed to prevent people from gathering around music made of "repetitive beats" (Weier, 2000). This contributed to a venue shift of raves from unlicensed venues to licensed ones like clubs (Anderson and Kavanaugh, 2008; Coomber et al., 2013). Despite rave culture being originally a free party culture that did not share neoliberal ideologies of accumulation of profit, its incorporation within the night time economy of mainstream club culture has led to raving becoming institutionalized (Thornton, 1996; Bennett, 2001). Today, 'underground' raves intended as 'semi-legal' parties run in unlicensed venues still exist, however, promoters often charge their crowd for entrance and drinks. Nevertheless, rave culture today still pretty much shares the concept of 'Utopian egalitarianism' (Thornton, 2013) to the

extent that it promotes 'safe' spaces without strict door policies where people would come together despite their ethnicity, class, background, gender, profession, age, sex, fashion and other social distinctions in an attempt to answer their human social needs and transcend the mundane of everyday life, while celebrating the ethos of 'Peace, Love, Unity, Respect' (PLUR) (Hunt et al., 2010).

As regards clubbing today, the type of music performed, as well as the characteristics of the setting such as the lights and the drugs involved make raving and clubbing very similar (Sanders, 2006; Coomber et al., 2013). Thornton (2013) argued that raving has become 'mainstream' to the extent that the development of new technologies has led to the music becoming more accessible and what was once the sound of underground raves and pirate radio stations could now be easily found at clubs and on the internet. Nevertheless, within the mainstream culture of raving and clubbing today you can find smaller 'underground' cultures or 'sub-scenes' that promote a certain type of music and fashion and therefore crowd (Sanders, 2006; Anderson and Kavanaugh, 2008). Here, the term 'underground' refers to a subcultural reality where you can find authentic sounds and styles that contrasts with the reality of the mass and the mainstream (Thornton, 2013). As Anderson and Kavanaugh (2008) suggest, rave culture today consists more in a 'rave-club culture continuum' where people coexist within underground raves and commercial nightclubs. Commercialization has therefore led to the emergence of the 'electronic dance music scene' (EDM), which has been used to describe this 'rave-club culture continuum' (Anderson and Kavanaugh, 2008). Here, participants of the EDM scene range from those who feel particularly close to the music and values of the raveera ethos and those who's participation is merely accidental or curious (Anderson and Kavanaugh, 2008). Finally, a study conducted by Hunt and colleagues (2010) shows that people who participate both at clubs and underground raves identify more with one than the other on the bases of music preferences, consumption practices, beliefs and use of drugs. According to Thornton (1996), the way nightlife participants shape their identities comes from the consumption practices shared by the scene they are the most involved in. For instance, participants in the study distinguish between underground raves and massive raves in terms of ethos, music and the normative behaviours of each scene and construct their identity upon underground and mainstream discourses (Hunt et al., 2010). Therefore, the focus of this dissertation will be the EDM scene in England where the participants chosen are familiar with both rave and club cultures.

2.3 Recreational Drug Use within the EDM Scene

Since their appearance in England in the late eighties and early nighties raves, and later clubs, have been targeted as sites of excessive risk by politicians, health practitioners, drug researchers (Hammersley et al., 1999; Merchant and MacDonald, 1994) and the media due to their relationship

with illicit drugs (Sanders, 2006; Hunt et al., 2009). The public concern has therefore led to a 'War on Drugs' with the implementation of the Criminal Justice and Public Order Act (1994); the Public Entertainment Licenses Drug Act (1997); Section 1 of the Antisocial Behavior Act (2003); and harm reduction strategies such as the Dance Drugs Alliance agency; the 'Safer Dancing' policy; and the Manchester City Council and Lifeline drugs agency (Sanders, 2006; Coomber et al., 2013). The terms 'club drugs' or 'dance drugs' refer to illicit substances with stimulant and/or hallucinogenic properties such as the prototypical rave drug ecstasy (MDMA), ketamine, marijuana, GHB, Rohypnol, LSD, psilocybin mushrooms, amphetamine, methamphetamine, and recently cocaine which use is predominantly limited to the settings of raves and clubs (Hunt et al., 2010; Thornton, 2013).

Studies by Measham and colleagues (1994, 1998) suggest that people who attend raves and clubs experiment with different drug combinations and enter a pattern of polydrug use (Hunt et al., 2009; Thornton, 2013; Boys et al., 2001). In this perspective, it has been observed that some ravers and clubbers engage in what has been described as 'concurrent polydrug use', which consists in ingesting different drugs on different occasions (Earleywine and Newcomb, 1997), as well as engaging in 'simultaneous polydrug use', which on the other hand consists in the ingestion of different drugs on the same occasion and which has been observed being a prevalent activity within the electronic dance music scene (Ives and Ghelani, 2006; Boys et al., 2001). Polydrug use as an activity strongly associated with the dance music scene has been observed following different 'stages' of the night out. For instance, ravers and clubbers would use different drugs depending on the phase prior to the arrival at the event, the event itself, and the after party on the purpose of achieving desirable effects (Malbon, 1999; Boys et al., 1997; Hunt et al., 2009). These observations contrast much of the epidemiological literature in the drug field (Miller et al., 2005; Kelly, 2005; Measham et al., 2001; Yacoubian and Wish 2006) to the extent that instead of portraying the user as someone passive and irresponsible it portrays them as active and rational actors who plan and negotiate their choices on the basis of maximizing benefits and reducing risks (Hunt et al., 2009; Williams and Parker, 2001). For instance, the qualitative study conducted by Hunt and colleagues (2009) in the San Francisco rave scene shows that combining different substances at different moments throughout the night function as 'extending' (i.e GHB and marijuana) and 'enhancing' (i.e marijuana, hallucinogens, ketamine) (Hammersley et al., 1999) the pleasurable effects of one drug such as ecstasy, as well as 'reducing' the negative effects of another drug (i.e cocaine to reduce alcohol intoxication) (Coomber et al., 2013). Nevertheless, among ravers and clubbers it has been observed how drug use also follows a more spontaneous and less planned pattern influenced by the 'rush of the moment' or by friends and other people within the rave or club settings (Hunt et al., 2009). Moreover, the study shows that the participant's choice of the drug and

the different combinations is based on peer knowledge, research and personal experience in order to manage the risks involved by applying harm reduction strategies (Hunt et al., 2009; Anderson and Kavanaugh, 2008). These findings are supported by Boys and colleagues' study (2001) which shows that cannabis, ecstasy, LSD, amphetamine, cocaine and alcohol are used to attain specific desirable effects such as 'enhancing activity', 'relax', 'feel better', 'keep going', 'feel euphoric', 'enjoy company', 'increase sociability', 'stay awake', 'stay intoxicated', and 'increase confidence' and that the combination of different drugs function as ameliorating or reducing specific drug effects. This perspective explains drug use as merely functional and rational based upon discourses of costs and benefits (Duff, 2008). Apart from these more immediate benefits of drug use such as 'enhancing the activity' or 'feeling euphoric', Hunt and colleagues (2010) observed that some users also display enduring effects that stem from their drug use such as engaging in more meaningful social relationships. It has also been argued that the relationship between illicit drugs and the dance music scene is somewhat related to the nature of its settings. In this perspective, the nature of the music, the lights and the general party atmosphere accommodates the use of dance drugs (Thornton, 1996; Sanders, 2006). An example provided by Coomber and colleagues (2013) is that hallucinogenics are often used to enhance the visuals and audio stimulus of the rave and club environments. Another aspect which seems being related to the high prevalence of dance drug users within club and rave settings is that due to the availability of the drugs as well as a general attitude of acceptability towards drug use within these settings makes drug use a normalized activity (Sanders, 2006; Maesham et al., 2001; Coomber et al., 2013).

As regards how people initiate their drug use, research shows that friends are usually those who give advices in terms of how, where, and when to use the drug (Grund 1993; Zinberg, 1984), as well as giving information about acceptable drug-use behaviours, which in turns regulates the drug using patterns of the new user and help facilitate enjoyable experiences (Sanders, 2006). For instance, heroin, crack and excessive drug use is generally seen within the rave music scene as unacceptable behaviours (Hunt and Evans, 2003). Furthermore, since raves and club events usually take place on the course of the weekend, it is not surprising that for the majority of ravers and clubbers their recreational drug use is also limited to weekends (Hammersley et al., 2002). Outside the rave-party reality of the weekend, ravers and clubbers are usually law-abiding citizens who conduct relatively busy lives and have responsibilities (Hunt et al., 2010). Studies about club drug use (Hammersley et al., 2002; Maesham et al., 2001) also show that many ravers and clubbers reduce or stop their drug use behaviour due to responsibilities of day-to-day life such as family responsibilities, employment responsibilities, and other life-course transitions such as getting older (Sanders, 2006).

Finally, in terms of prevalence of dance drug patterns among users between 16- to 24-year-olds within the EDM scene in England, results from the British Crime Survey (BCS) (2011) show that users who attend nightclubs and raves are more likely than nonattendees to take illicit drugs and that higher rates of drug use are identified among regular ravers and clubbers (Coomber et al., 2013). Moreover, a survey founded by the Home Office in the UK shows that the lifetime prevalence rate for clubbers and ravers use of any dance drug is 79 per cent (Coomber et al., 2013). Other studies in the US have also found an association with the type of music performed at clubs and the patterns of drug use among attendees. Results show that people who attend electronic music nightclubs display higher rates of drug use compared to people who attend hip hop nightclubs (Coomber et al., 2013). Finally, in today's electronic dance music scene the prevalence of men and women using dance drugs is almost similar with a ratio of 60-40 (Hunt et al., 2010).

2.4 The Meanings Underlying Recreational Drug Use within the EDM Scene

Within the field of alcohol and drug research (AOD) and the involvement of these illicit substances within the leisure activities of adults and young people, much of the focus has been put upon descriptive characteristics of the user and the substances, as well as upon risk and protective factors (Race, 2017, Moore, 2008). This epidemiological approach, which relies upon the collection of quantitative data, fails to explain the reasons underlying drug consumption to the extent that it considers the user as relatively passive and therefore fails to place them within the social context of drug use (Hunt et al., 2010; Duff, 2008). For these reasons, this section will consider the approach of cultural studies research and will explore discourses around the pleasures, solidarity, and subjectivity within the social context of the EDM scene in order to understand the meanings that ravers and clubbers associate to their drug use.

Research on the pleasures of drug consumption (Duff, 2008; Fitzgerald, 2002; Levy et al., 2005; Race, 2017) suggests that people are essentially hedonistic in their drug use.¹ In this perspective, two bodies of research have attempted to explain drug-related pleasures: the first (Boys et al., 2001; Hammersley et al., 1999), sees pleasure as the consequence of rational thinking based upon a cost-benefit analysis of drug use such as 'enhance activity' or 'increase sociability' (Coomber et al., 2013). The second body of research (Duff, 2008; Maesham et al., 2001; Fitzgerald, 1997; Thrift, 2003; Keane 2002), which is more relevant for the purposes of this dissertation, empathizes the importance of the social context in the social construction of drug-related pleasures. Here, Duff (2008) and Zinberg (1984) suggest that the

¹ According to Duff (2008), hedonism refers to the pursuit of pleasure and 'sensational experiences'.

pleasures that stem from the drug are not exclusively related to the properties of the drug itself but to the corporeal and performative practices that the drug facilitates within a specific social context. This approach assumes that individuals might experience different levels of drug-related pleasures depending on the type of drug consumed as well as the context in which the individual is consuming. In the context of raves and clubs, the performative practice of dancing, that is facilitated by the use of ecstasy and other dance drugs and by the music and the general atmosphere of the setting, has been described by participants as a very pleasurable and ecstatic experience to the extent that they could feel a deeper connection with one's own body (Duff, 2008; Malbon, 1999). Other participants in Duff's (2005) study emphasized the pleasures of 'shared collectivity' (Malbon, 1999) that stem from the feelings of solidarity and connection with friends and strangers through social² interactions facilitated by the drugs. Here, ecstasy, cocaine and amphetamine enabled people to open up and engage in more meaningful conversations with friends as well as becoming more confident when talking with strangers, which contributed to the development of a 'sense of belonging' and 'community' (Malbon 1999; Thornton 1996; Bennett, 2001). Taking into account what has been discussed so far, therefore, Duff (2005), Malbon (1999), and Thrift (2000) argue that one of the reasons why ravers and clubbers use dance drugs is that these enhance and facilitate activities that enable them to connect better with people and one's self and which in turn are highly pleasurable.

Nevertheless, in order to understand drug-related pleasures it is important to consider the settings in which they are embedded (Maesham et al., 2001; Thrift 2003; DeLanda, 2005). In this perspective, DeLanda (2005) argues that people can experience spaces in 'intensive ways', meaning that some spaces have the potential to create intensive sensory and perceptual experiences which in turn enable feelings of affection towards them. This concept in relation to drug-related pleasures within the settings of raves and clubs can be understood in the way that clubs and raves constitutes energetic spaces characterized by intensive lights and sounds where individuals connect with through practices such as dancing and interacting with others enhanced by the use of dance drugs (Duff, 2008). This also offers an explanation of why the same drug can be experienced differently according to the setting in which it is consumed (Holt and Treloar, 2008).

Finally, dance drugs enable drug related pleasures through experiencing the body differently in terms of corporeal and psychological sensations (Fitzgerald, 1997; Beck and Rosenbaum, 1994; Hunt et al., 2010). For instance, In Duff's (2005) study and in Hunt and colleagues' (2010) study, participants

² According to Durkheim (1963), solidarity can be understood in terms of an individual's personal and 2 emotional attachment to a group (Anderson and Kavanaugh, 2008).

described how ecstasy, cocaine, amphetamine and other dance drugs enhanced the way they perceived the environment (i.e the music, the lights) and their body (i.e they could dance for longer periods). These Psychophysiological sensations, which seems being caused particularly by the chemical properties of the drug and therefore independent from what the individual wants to achieve from the drug experience (Keane, 2002), provide an explanation of polydrug use among ravers and clubbers, which can be understood as a motive to experience new sensations through new combinations of drugs (Duff, 2008). In their study, Hunt and colleagues (2010) add an emotional component of drugged related pleasures. They argue that ecstasy, for instance, impacts the emotional state of the user by making them feel free to act (i.e dancing) as they really are without being constrained by the societal expectations of everyday life social behaviour. Within the rave and club realities, and with the use of dance drugs, individuals are able to transform conventional notions of privacy, conformity, social and personal behaviour and enable self-expression through dancing, fashion and social interactions, which offers them an escape route from the reality of day to day life (Reynolds, 1999). Finally, in a different perspective, Anderson and Kavanaugh (2008) suggest that drug use within the EDM scene enables what they define as 'social affective solidarity' that relates to the concept of connection and belonging previously discussed. According to Duff (2008):

“By examining the context in which drug use takes place can we begin to understand the ways in which assessments about risks and pleasures emerge and take meaning” (p.296).

Chapter 3: Methodology

3.1 Introduction

As previously mentioned in the literature review, the majority of the epidemiological research concerned with the involvement of illicit drugs within the leisure activities of adults and young people has been focusing on shaping a general picture of the characteristics of the user and their drug related behaviours, as well as the problematic associated to their drug use (Race, 2017, Moore, 2008; Shiner and Newburn, 1997; Hunt et al., 2010). Quantitative survey data have therefore been the means through which policy and health practitioners have sought to identify drug related risks in order to develop intervention strategies. Studies conducted by Kelly (2005), Yacoubian and Wish (2006), and Boys and colleagues (2001), have pictured the user as someone who's behaviour is fundamentally rational and determined by a cost-benefit analysis. However, this has failed to consider the context in which drug use takes place and the meanings that people attach to it (Hunt et al., 2010; Duff, 2008). To achieve the purposes of this dissertation, that is exploring the meanings underlying recreational drug use within the EDM scene in England, data have been collected through qualitative research methods such as in-depth face-to-face interviews (FtF) (Brennen, 2022; Opdenakker, 2006). This allowed to give a voice to the participants on the issue of drug use based upon their lived experiences and involvement in the dance scene. Data have then been analysed through the perspective of cultural study research and in particular through the 'situated (Maesham et al., 2001; Thrift 2003; DeLanda, 2005), affective (Malbon, 1999; Duff, 2008), social (Thornton, 1996; Bennett, 2001), and performative' (Duff, 2007; Zinberg, 1984) dimensions of drug use discussed in section '2.4' of the literature review.

3.2 Research Strategy

Qualitative data research has been chosen for the purposes of this dissertation because it includes "information about feelings, values and attitudes", (David and Sutton, 2004: 35). By conducting qualitative research in the form of in-depth face-to-face interviews, it enables the researcher to create a relationship of trust with the interviewee which facilitates the collection of data on a topic that many could find uncomfortable to discuss (Opdenakker, 2006). This approach is advantageous to the extent that it offers an opportunity to people to share their experiences and feelings about a topic without being judged and which helps the researcher gain a deeper understanding of the social and cultural realities in which individuals constantly negotiate their choices and shape their behaviours. This also helps emphasize the complexities of human reasoning and behaviour without limiting it to distinguished patterns determined on the basis of a 'yes' or 'no' answers like quantitative survey data do

(Opdenakker, 2006). It is worth pointing out that this type of method to gather qualitative data leaves space for interpretation and analysis to the researcher who then constructs conceptual and theoretical knowledge based upon the meaningful stories of the interviewee (Dicicco and Crabtree, 2006). In order to make sure that all relevant information has been collected, the interviews for this dissertation have been tape-recorded and transcribed with the approval of the interviewee. Finally, in-depth face-to-face interviews allows the investigator to take advantage of relevant information that stem from the 'non verbal interaction' with the participant, like body language and intonation, as well as efficiently overcoming potential misunderstandings (Shiner and Newburn, 1997). As regards the type of the interview chosen, an in-depth semi-structured interview has been considered more appropriate for the purposes of this project. The reasons why the researcher has decided to design an in-depth semi-structured type of interview, which consists in predetermined open-ended questions, is to give the freedom to the interviewee to raise relevant areas of interest as well as giving the opportunity to the researcher to formulate new questions based upon the flow of the conversation (Dicicco and Crabtree, 2006). Finally, because of the way they are designed, semi-structured interviews generate a more diversified set of data that varies across interviewees. It is important to point out that the researcher must acknowledge that the meanings of a social phenomenon or behaviour explored through qualitative research methods might differ across cultures. Cultures that not necessarily refer to the culture of a country but also to the culture of a specific group or community. This means that participants might explain a phenomenon in different ways according to the cultural significance attached to it, which in turn might produce different levels of analysis and interpretation for the researcher (Hammarberg et al., 2016).

3.3 Sample

A snowball sampling has been chosen for the purposes of this dissertation. The researcher started with two people from their social network that they knew are actively involved within the EDM scene in England and that also like to experiment with recreational drugs at raves and clubs. The researcher has then asked their initial participants to refer other contacts who also fit with the research criteria and who might be willing to participate in this research (Parker and Geddes 2019). In this way, the researcher was able to recruit two additional participants actively involved within the EDM scene and familiar with dance drugs. The sample was therefore composed of four people, of which two males and two females.

Snowball sampling is a good method for the purposes of this dissertation because it enables the researcher to access populations who's behavior is unconventional and stigmatized, as it is the case for

the participants of this research who engage with recreational drugs (Handcock and Gile, 2011). The parameters of the sample were therefore defined according to specific characteristics (i.e use of dance drugs) and group membership (i.e involvement in the EDM scene). There are criticisms in regards to snowball sampling due to the biased selection of the initial sample (Parker and Geddes, 2019). It is understood that by nature snowball sampling has a tendency of being biased, because it relies upon the participants chosen within the researcher's social network. The researcher chooses the sample according to specific characteristics that better fit with the purposes of their research, prioritizing therefore some individuals more than others. Finally, participants for this dissertation were recruited via messages and social media exchanges.

3.4 Reflection

As an insider within the EDM scene in England, as well as being accepted and recognized by participants as being part of this culture, the researcher was able to engage in more meaningful conversations during the interviews for this research. This closeness with the participants allowed them to feel more comfortable when disclosing their experiences with recreational drugs which enabled the researcher to gather important information for the analysis. The researcher's insider knowledge, which comes from a shared identity, language and experiential base with the sample, has helped on the process of interpretation and analysis because thanks to their social insights they could better contextualize the experiences of the participants within the rave and club realities (Chammas, 2020; Taylor, 2011). As an insider researcher, it was easy to avoid what is known as 'culture shock' which often causes judgments and stereotypes among researchers who are unfamiliar with the culture or group under study (Greene, 2014). Nevertheless, there are some challenges that insider researchers might face when researching about a group or community of which they are part of or identify with. For instance, the researcher could be subject to 'insider bias' by prioritizing the information that confirm their views, beliefs, values and experiences on the topic under investigation, while neglecting relevant information that could be useful for further discussion (Taylor, 2011). This comes from the researcher being too subjective, which narrows the attention to specific information and which makes assumptions more likely to occur (Greene, 2014). Despite their closeness and familiarity with the area of research, the researcher for this dissertation was able to overcome potential biases by relying exclusively upon the data gathered by the participants' experiences and by adopting an objective view on the topic of research. Furthermore, potential biases were minimized through the practice of 'self-reflexivity', which has led the researcher to take into account the way their insider knowledge impacts the research and its participants (Greene, 2014).

Another issue that it is worth pointing out when doing qualitative research as an insider is related to the impact of friendship upon the processes involved in the research, including the collection of data and the process of interpretation. In the case of this research, the initial sample chosen by the researcher came from the researcher's friendships group. It is more appropriate therefore to talk about 'intimate insider researcher' (Taylor, 2011), due to the nature of the friendship with the initial participants of the snowball sample. The advantages of being an intimate insider researcher is that the friend informant felt more comfortable in disclosing intimate experiences with recreational drugs which helped the researcher gather a high amount of qualitative data. Nevertheless, in some instances there were periods of 'random talking' during the interviews which also led to gather irrelevant information. It is worth pointing out that many ethical considerations have been taken into account throughout the research concerning both the nature of the friendship with some of the participants as well as the nature of drug use. In this regard, the researcher ensured to minimize potential physical and psychological harm during the interviews, as well as situations that might create discomfort or emotional distress. For some people drug use is a very delicate topic, especially if discourses about addiction and overdose are involved. Perhaps, some people might know someone who have died of overdose or might have experienced addiction directly. For these reasons, the researcher also ensured that confidentiality was kept throughout the all process of research and that consent was provided by all participants prior to the research. In this way, participants were informed about the purposes of the research as well as their right to withdraw at any stage of the research (British Society of Criminology Statement of Ethics, 2015).

Chapter 4: Analysis & Discussion

4.1 Introduction

From the late 80s and early 90s to today, drug use has been a central characteristic of rave culture and the EDM scene in general. As discussed previously in this dissertation, raves and clubs have been targeted as sites of excessive risk in which drug use is seen as irrational and pathological (Hammersley et al., 1999; Merchant and MacDonald, 1994; Hunt et al., 2009). The perspective of cultural studies research explored in the literature review, however, offered a different approach to the one shared by the epidemiological research by placing the user within their social context (Duff, 2008; Fitzgerald, 2002; Levy et al., 2005; Race, 2017). It is in this way that drug use becomes more complex and takes meaning. This dissertation, therefore, explored the literature around the reasoning behind recreational drug use, including poly drug use and assessments of risks and benefits, as well as the literature around drug related pleasures within the context of raves and clubs. In this section, this project will analyze the data gathered from the interviews of this qualitative research. Two main themes will lead the discussion and analysis; the first will explore 'Drug related pleasures as a consequence of rational thinking', focusing on the discourses of risk management and normalization; whereas the second theme will explore the 'Social context of drug related pleasures', focusing on the performative, social, spacial, and emotional dimensions of pleasure.

4.2 Drug Related Pleasures as a Consequence of Rational Thinking

The starting point of the analysis is to define the social context of the participants where their drug use takes place. In this regard, all of the participants share the similar experience of experimenting with recreational drugs for the first time within the context of raves, clubs and festivals, finding themselves within the rave-club culture continuum discussed by Anderson and Kavanaugh (2008).

Participant A: The time came few months later (first drug experience), (...).

Because we were going to a rave and lots of friends were going to be there.

Participant C: I have been interested to explore and experiment with recreational drugs because I was introduced to some of these substances by a lot of people and friends over the years and that was within the rave and club settings.

Participant B: When I went with some friends to this festival (...) there was a random Australian guy selling pills, (...).

Participant D: I went to a festival and (...). I got approached one of the nights at the festival and I got offered the drugs. (...).

When asked whether they experiment with recreational drugs outside the rave and club settings, the participants' answers suggest that their drug use is predominantly limited to weekends and to the context of the dance scene:

Participant A: I would only do recreational drugs if it was psychedelics, outside of the club and rave contexts.

Participant B: I wouldn't do it on a week day or on a calm night.

Participant D: I don't see the point in doing it outside the context of the night out.

Only Participant C claimed to enjoy experimenting with drugs in different contexts:

Participant C: Yeah, experimenting in different settings has always been my kind of thing.

These testimonies suggest that outside the weekend reality dominated by the nighttime economy of raves and clubs, participants of the EDM scene lead normal lives and have responsibilities (Hunt et al., 2010):

Participant A: I try to implement, you know, my five a days and try not to drink alcohol in the week. I try to find balance.

Participant B: I have started this new job, so I care about my performance that I wouldn't go out on a crazy one on Sunday night, knowing that I have work the next day.

Participant D: During the week, I'll be working or I play football.

Some even start to grow out of the scene and their drug use due to life course transitions such as getting older (Sanders, 2006; Hammersley et al., 2002; Maesham et al., 2001).

Participant C: Now I'm quite old and I'm starting to grow out from that.

The context of drug use being defined, which as mentioned earlier takes place within the rave-club culture continuum, this analysis will now explore drug related pleasures as a consequence of rational thinking. In this regard, recreational drug use among all the participants seem to follow a rational path, determined by a cost versus benefit analysis in order to achieve desirable effects, while managing potential risks (Hunt et al., 2009; Williams and Parker, 2001; Duff, 2008; Boys et al., 2001; Malbon, 1999):

Participant A: I do them to enhance an experience or just to give me the energy to stay up all night because I've got a gig.

Participant A: I often use amphetamines like speed, because I've got a bit of ADHD, it keeps me focused and makes me feel like I've got control over my night and myself and I perform better.

In the case of participant A, who is a DJ, the amphetamines function as achieving the desirable effect of 'staying awake' and 'perform better', supporting the findings of Boys and colleagues' study (2001). Even simultaneous poly drug use, which is a practice shared by all of the participants, functions as maximizing the benefits and minimizing the risks or the undesirable effects of another drug (Coomber et al., 2013; Hammersley et al., 1999; Boys et al., 2001):

Participant A: Unless like, I'm having a, you know, a bad trip, I need some amphetamines to sober me up, because that's what speed does to me, It sobers me up.

Participant B: I've learned what drug to take to feel specific things or to balance out the effects of another drug.

Participant C: Also if you're doing drugs like ketamine, for example, I always make sure I have some speed as a backup, if I knew that I was getting into a bit of a wobbly place then speed would level it out.

Taking into account the above, it seems that participants of the EDM scene actively negotiate their choices in order to achieve pleasurable experiences, which includes being aware of potential dangers that might interfere with their hedonistic goals (Hunt et al., 2009). Participants also minimize the risks involved through researching about drugs as well as through peer knowledge and personal experience which determines their drug choices (Hunt et al., 2009; Anderson and Kavanaugh, 2008).

Participant A: I was prepared for what was coming, I had researched it, I felt like I was sensible enough to try it, I had the best time ever.

Participant A: I didn't know the consequences of doing too much ketamine. And one time, I 'K holed' so badly, that honestly like made me feel really bad...it also gave me the confidence to 'Okay, this time, I'm not going to do that much because it's going to make me feel bad'.

Participant B: I think like especially at first, when you start to learn like how much you can do or how much not to do.

Participant B: You also get to know about risks through other people, you know, you kind of pass down the information and you learn from it.

Participant C: I just feel like besides you're own experience you also learn from other people's experiences and advices.

Participant D: I feel like if you manage your control as best as you can, then if it is bad, you'd be able to feel it. And now with the years (...), I feel like I have some knowledge.

As noted by all of the participants, knowing and researching about drugs function as protective factors to potential un-pleasurable experiences (Anderson and Kavanaugh, 2008). Another protective factor that has been frequently mentioned is being surrounded by friends, which makes them feel safer while experimenting with drugs (Grund, 1993):

Participant A: Because we were going to a rave and lots of friends were going to be there. And I felt safe doing it.

Participant B: When I went with some friends to this festival (...). It felt like relatively safe space to experiment with drugs.

Participant D: I went to a festival and (...). Everyone was like, you know, we're all together, we're friends, we're camping together, we felt safe.

Participant B and C explain how the type of event and the music play an important role in determining the choice of the drug, emphasizing the relationship between recreational drugs and the setting in which they are consumed (Thornton, 1996; Sanders, 2006):

Participant B: Sometimes Yeah, you can just take k on like a chill kind of slow down tempo thing and it's kind of perfect.

Participant C: The choice of the drugs depends on the different music or vibes or the state of mind I'm in.

Other times, however, the choice of the drug seem to follow a more casual and spontaneous path influenced by the people around (Hunt et al., 2009):

Participant D: The idea of it to me now is quite casual. Sometimes I'd just go for what my friends decide.

Finally, because of the high prevalence of dance drugs and the general attitude of acceptance towards them, all of the participants agree that recreational drug use within the EDM scene has become normalized:

Participant A: This scene and this industry is fuelled by drugs (...).

Participant B: Yeah, I think so... the festival I've been mentioning, (...) there is a space where they sell drugs and you can just walk over and buy whatever you need.

Participant C: But yeah it is normalized within the EDM scene because first of all the majority of the people involved do drugs, and also when it comes to the attitude towards drug use is generally an accepted behaviour.

Participant D: Yeah, I think so. Because everyone knows that exists.(...). I've met people that don't try to do the drugs, but they still accept that their friends and everyone does them.

Moreover, two of the participants pointed out how normalization of recreational drugs could lead to safer drug use within the EDM scene, contributing therefore to minimize drug related risks while maximizing the benefits:

Participant D: I think if we gave time and efforts towards exploring drugs and getting to a medical level where you can control it and give people advice on how to use it and make sure that dosages are safe, then you'd be very safe to use within clubs.

Participant B: I think that normalizing drugs is the only way to make drug use safer.

From these testimonies, therefore, it can be said that pleasurable experiences that stem from recreational drug use are determined by the participants' rational choices based upon maximizing the benefits while minimizing potential risks (Hunt et al.2009; Williams and Parker, 2001). In this regard, the testimonies suggest that simultaneous poly drug use functions as enhancing an experience or reducing the effects of a less pleasurable experience (Coomber et al., 2013; Hammersley et al., 1999; Boys et al., 2001). Other rational practices that minimize drug related risks while facilitating positive drug related experiences are researching about drugs as well as learning from personal experiences and from others (Anderson and Kavanaugh, 2008; Hunt et al., 2009). Furthermore, the participants emphasized the importance of being surrounded by friends which provides a safe environment to experiment with drugs (Grund, 1993). Finally, the participants agree about drug use being normalized within the scene (Sanders, 2006; Maesham et al., 2001; Coomber et al., 2013), suggesting that this might contribute towards safer drug use in the future.

4.3 Social Context of Drug Related Pleasures

The previous section has explored drug related pleasures as the consequence of rational choices made upon a benefit versus cost analysis. In this regard, pleasure was understood in terms of 'benefit' such as staying up for longer or enhancing an experience, which could be achieved by minimizing potential risks. This section will now focus on drug related pleasures in relation to the social context of raves and clubs. In this case, pleasure does not follow a rational path but manifests itself in different forms

according to the nature of the social context in which the drug experience takes place (Duff, 2008; Maesham et al., 2001; Fitzgerald, 1997). This concept was further emphasised by two participants who pointed out how drug experiences are very subjective and depends on the social context in which they are embedded:

Participant B: It's funny because I started like doing drugs and like people's reactions are so different. I think just because like obviously, like body predispositions and like different psychological reactions to situations.

Participant A: It's very subjective. Some people might, you know, be ready and have the best time and have a really good introduction to drugs.

These two statements point out how it is not only the drug itself that determines the different drug experiences but these experiences are determined by both individual and contextual factors (Duff, 2008; Zinberg, 1984). In this regard, this analysis will start by exploring the experience or practice of dancing on drugs which has been observed being common to all the participants:

Participant B: Dancing, it's like, the perfect act of play. Because you're moving without purpose, technically, without clear direction, (...) I think there is no purpose just moving South. I think that dancing is great on drugs because it allows you to play with your body in different ways.

Participant A: Drugs change the way you behave to music, you know, you just take some drugs and dancing becomes a way of expressing yourself or a conflict, (...). You just dance and it feels amazing.

Participant C: Like this is your Sunday church, if you go into a space where a lot of people dance and have these emotional experiences, I feel like there's some similar energy to when you go into a church even if you're not religious.

Participant D: Especially with MDMA, there's more of a link to the music. When I take MDMA I feel like you really feel involved with the music more and you dance more.

These testimonies link to what Duff (2008) and Zinberg (1984) defined as the 'corporeal and performative practice of drug related pleasures'. In this perspective, therefore, dance drugs facilitate a deeper connection and interaction with the music and one's body, making dancing a very pleasurable experience (Malbon, 1999; Fitzgerald, 1997; Hunt et al., 2010). The performative practice of dancing also provides a way for individuals to express themselves and act freely (Reynolds, 1999), as pointed out by participant A. Finally, dance drugs also enable other corporeal pleasures through connecting with one's body in terms of psychophysiological sensations (Fitzgerald, 1997, Hunt et al., 2010):

Participant C: That's a lot more ketamine orientated. And yeah, it's a lot more introspective you know, it enables you to explore some of the inner workings of your mind.

In this case, the properties of ketamine enabled participant C to create a deeper connection with their body and mind (Keane, 2002). As regards other practices that dance drugs facilitate, the testimonies suggest that social interactions with friends and strangers become stronger on drugs:

Participant B: The environment of the festival or whatever other party kind of environment which also involves the use of drugs kind of thought me that you can just have an open and honest conversation with people, even if you don't know them.

Participant D: When I'm interacting with my friends on drugs, I feel more like love and likeliness for them. You know, I just want to talk to them more, have more fun (...).

According to Duff (2005), Malbon (1999), and Thornton (2013), these interactions that take place at raves and clubs and which are facilitated by dance drugs allow to create a deeper and meaningful connection with people and a sense of belonging to a community, leading to what they defined as 'pleasure of shared collectivity', or as Anderson and Kavanaugh (2008) referred to as 'Social affective solidarity':

Participant A: I just started to serve a different mindset towards the scene since I started using drugs. It wasn't necessarily a toxic one, but more of a spiritual sense of belonging to your community and having, you know, all these people to connect with.

Participant B: They can cause addiction, they also can give such good meanings to life and bring people together that they wouldn't get together necessarily, especially if they're coming from different cultures, different backgrounds, is crazy how like they feel united through, you know, this culture that is fuelled by drugs.

Participant C: For me is just meeting a lot of similar like minded people, and just yeah, just feeling like this is a real community (...).

Participants also suggest how influential the setting is upon their drug experiences, emphasizing the relationship between the individual and the space explored by DeLanda (2005):

Participant A: I wouldn't really do MDMA outside during a walk and like, you know, it wouldn't be the right kind of setting, I think it would just make me anxious.

Participant B: It was kind of a surreal experience because of the type of music in that type of environment.

Participant C: I was on the ketamine and I just had this really ecstatic experience where I felt like very emotional and I think that this also came from the way the setting was design you know, with the projections as well as the type of the music.

Participant D: Let's say MDMA, I'll say the first point is for the enjoyment and pleasure of music, like, it makes your senses more sensitive.

In this regard, it seems that dance drugs enable people to experience the space differently by making the senses more sensitive, as pointed out by participant D. In the case of raves and clubs, therefore, the intensive lights and the music which define the setting, work together to create energetic spaces which, together with dance drugs, enable to create intensive perceptual and sensory experiences that connects people to the space (DeLanda, 2005; Duff, 2005; Hunt et al., 2010). In this perspective, it is the interaction between the space and the individual who is under the influence of drugs that facilitates pleasurable practices like dancing and interacting with friends. The importance of space when it comes to drug related pleasures, therefore, explains why drug use is highly prevalent within the contexts of raves and clubs (Coomber et al., 2013). Finally, the testimonies suggest that the rave and club realities which include energetic spaces and the use of dance drugs, offer an escape route from the day-to-day life where people are free to act as they really are (Reynolds, 1999; Hunt et al., 2010):

Participant A: There is a layer of stress and like anxiety that is caused by everyday life that just vanishes when you go out and have fun. So definitely a form of escapism, and also a form of connecting with people and connecting with your creativity.

Participant B: I feel like raves and clubs are spaces where you can actually be yourself, and obviously drugs facilitate this to some extent.

Participant C: But yeah, definitely recreational drugs kind of allow you to loosen up (...). The biggest thing for me is the these settings are a bit far removed a bit more remote and outside of the general kind of day to day kind of framework.

Participant D: The weekend is kind of seen as like a time where you can do something different and enjoy yourself in a different way. And music and the drugs helped me to enjoy myself, to cut off from everything I do during the week.

Taking into account the cultural studies approach in the field of drug related pleasures, this analysis has placed the participant's drug use within the social context of the EDM scene in England, which as it has been previously pointed out consists in a rave-club culture continuum that takes place during the weekends (Anderson and Kavanaugh, 2008; Hammersley et al., 2002). Here, the testimonies have provided evidence in support of the existing research, which argues that drug use follows an hedonistic path influenced by the dynamics of the social context in which it takes place (Duff, 2007; Maesham et al., 2001; Fitzgerald, 1997; Thrift, 2003; Keane 2002). Nevertheless, the previous section has also provided evidence that besides being hedonistic in nature, recreational drug use for participants of the EDM scene follows a rational path based upon a cost versus benefit analysis which purpose is maximizing pleasurable experiences while minimizing potential risks. In this perspective, the testimonies are good evidence of how users actively negotiate their choices and shape their drug use. Finally, by taking into account the perspective of cultural study research, this analysis has provided an understanding of the meanings underlying recreational drug use within the EDM scene in England.

Chapter 5: Conclusion

By reviewing the literature within the cultural studies tradition in the field of drug use and the dance scene, as well as taking into account the drug experiences of the participants interviewed, this dissertation explored motivations for drug consumption within underground raves and commercial nightclubs. What are the meanings underlying recreational drug use for EDM participants? What are they hoping to achieve when using drugs at raves and clubs? Taking into account that a discourse on 'pathology' and the problematics of drug use was inappropriate to study a part of the population who's drug use is limited to the reality of their night time leisure, this dissertation has focused on a discourse on the pleasures of consumption within the rave and club realities. This dissertation argues therefore that recreational drug use is a mean to which EDM participants satisfy their 'hedonistic desires'. People enjoy taking drugs at raves and clubs because it enables them to connect better with people, their bodies and the space around, providing them with an escape route from the mundane of day-to-day life. In this regard, this dissertation argues that raves and clubs represent alternative realities where enjoyment and excitement become the ultimate goals, achieved through the consumption of illicit drugs. In this 'alternative world', therefore, the routines are interrupted and the social structures of societies are temporally forgotten, leaving space for personal autonomy, self-expression, self-actualization, and freedom.

By considering the social context of drug use and the lived experiences of the participants interviewed, this dissertation has offered an alternative view to the one of the official discourses and the epidemiological tradition, contributing therefore in filling the gaps within the cultural studies scholarship. In this regard, this research argues that too much attention has been put upon the problematics associated to drug use and emphasized by the epidemiological tradition such as risk of overdose in commercial nightclubs and risk of addiction in the long term. This approach takes for granted the importance of the social context and fails to provide explanations for recreational drug use. EDM participants are already aware of the dangers of consuming drugs and have already developed harm-reduction strategies. They are active and rational individuals who for the majority of their time lead normal lives, maintain jobs and have responsibilities, fitting within the social structures of day-to-day society. For the majority of them, their drug use is limited to weekends and to the rave and club realities, for this reason a discourse on pathology is inappropriate. Acknowledging the fact that drugs will always be part of the EDM scene and rave culture, future research concerned with the risks associated to drug use could better focus on developing strategies that make drug use a safer activity,

while avoiding to stigmatize a part of the population who does not relate to problematics such as addiction and overdose. Similarly, research within the cultural studies tradition could better investigate the link between normalization and safer drug use at dance events, including festivals and other mass events that are often targeted as sites of excessive risk by official discourses.

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Appendix: Interview Guide

Interview Guide

Although the following interview questions are structured in a determinate way, this does not mean that the researcher stuck to this structure throughout the all process of the interview. As the interviews are semi-structured, some of the questions came up with the flow of the conversation with the interviewees. This ensured the collection of a very diversified range of qualitative data.

The meanings attached to recreational drug use within the EDM scene

Can you tell me about your favorite drug/s and tell me why it is your favorite?

What are the pleasurable experiences that stem from the use of recreational drugs within the rave and club realities?

Do you think that drug use within the EDM scene today is normalized?

Involvement in the electronic dance music (EDM) scene.

Tell me something about your interest and participation in the EDM scene

In your opinion, what differentiates underground raves from mainstream clubs?

What do you think is so appealing about raves and clubs?

Reasoning behind Recreational drug use within the EDM scene

How did you get introduced to recreational drugs ?

On a night out, do you experiment with more than one drug?

What is the purpose of combining different drugs at raves and clubs?

What influences the choice of the drug and the drug combinations you will consume?

Do you also experiment with drugs outside the context of raves and clubs?

Do you ever consider drug related risks when using drugs in these settings?